

1 APPENDIX 1: SUPPLEMENTARY DISCUSSION

2 Here, we provide some additional results and conclusions—especially regarding the
3 discrepancies between previous studies and ours. For data and code, please visit Dryad Digital
4 Repository: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.kwh70rz9t>. Our sequencing reads are available from
5 the NCBI SRA (PRJNA624762).

6

7 *Lineages K+L: population structure, non-monophyly, and gene flow with Lineage M*

8 Kozak et al. (2006) recovered an mtDNA lineage (Lineage K) from a single location in
9 Louisiana that was sister to Lineages M and L. In all of our phylogenetic analyses, our samples
10 from this region (E121–E124) were nested within samples from Lineage L (Figs. 3–4, S7);
11 likewise, our other analyses (e.g., Structure, PCA) revealed the close relationship between these
12 populations (Figs. 3–4, S5–S6). Thus, we grouped Lineage L and Lineage K together for most
13 purposes in this study and referred to them collectively as Lineage K+L. This result has some
14 relevance for future taxonomic revisions to this group. The type locality for *E. cirrigera* is “near
15 New Orleans, Louisiana, USA” (Green 1831), but the existence of extant populations close to
16 New Orleans is uncertain.

17 Within Lineage K+L, we found some evidence for introgression from Lineage M in our
18 phylogenetic network, PCA, Structure analyses (Figs. 3–4, S3, S5). This was especially true for
19 samples from Atlantic drainages (e.g., E002, E075, and E054), which overlap with the
20 geographic region from which previous authors have suggested morphological intermediacy
21 between these species (Howell and Switzer 1953). We recovered one of these samples (E054) as
22 sister to the remainder of Lineage K+L in ML phylogenies (Fig. 3), but it clustered with samples
23 from Lineage M in Structure and PCA analyses (Figs. 3, S4).

24 Today, Lineages M and K+L occur in sympatry and syntopy in several river drainages
25 across the Appalachian foothills (Camp et al. 2000; Kozak and Montanucci 2001; Pierson et al.
26 2021). These contact zones are near, but not perfectly aligned with, river drainage divides and
27 may reflect the result of gradual drainage migration or an ecological determination of species
28 distributions (Marshall 2000; Pierson et al. 2021). Phylogenetic networks and PCAs suggest that
29 at least some populations of these two groups have experienced historic hybridization, although
30 the extent of ongoing gene flow is unclear (Marshall 2000; Kozak and Montanucci 2001). In at
31 least some locations, these two occur today in syntopy with no genomic evidence for
32 hybridization (Pierson et al. 2021). This—and many of the other examples described in this
33 appendix—underscores the fact that our support for $K = 2$ in our Structure analyses including all
34 samples (Figs. 3, S5) does not provide strong evidence for only two distinct species in this group;
35 instead, this likely reflects the tendency for this type of model selection to favor the coarsest
36 categorization of hierarchical genetic structure, necessitating additional analysis of substructure
37 within these groups (Janes et al. 2017).

38

39 *Lineage M: population structure and admixture with Lineages E2, J, and L*

40 Of all mtDNA lineages, we had the largest sample size of Lineage M. We recovered
41 hierarchical genetic structure within this group and evaluated interactions with neighboring
42 lineages. Here, we focus on describing interactions with Lineages E2, J, and L.

43 Kozak et al. (2006) demonstrated the syntopy of Lineage E2 and Lineage M at one
44 locality in the upper Linville River drainage of western North Carolina. This is the location of a
45 smaller hypothesized drainage reorganization event, in which the Catawba River drainage's
46 Linville River captured its headwaters from the Tennessee River drainage's upper Toe River

47 (Weaver 1897). One estimate of the timing of this event places it between the late Jurassic and
48 Cretaceous (Judson 1975)—far too early to be relevant for the syntopy of these two lineages of
49 *Eurycea*—but this is inconsistent with biological data suggesting a more recent date (Ramsey
50 1965; Thoma 2005). We included the samples from Kozak et al. (2006) in this study (Lineage
51 E2: E097, E098; Lineage M: E102), and we recovered the same lineage assignments for each,
52 with no sign of additional introgression into Lineage E2 (e.g., Figs. 3, S5). Thus, although the
53 genomes of Lineage E2 include introgressed alleles from the southern clade, the two appear to be
54 reproductively isolated at this modern contact zone. This further underscores the inadequacy of
55 the name *E. wilderae* to reflect the distinct evolutionary history of each group.

56 In one sample (E025) nearest the contact zone between Lineage M and Lineage J, we
57 found strong evidence of admixture. This sample fell out within Lineage M in the uncensored
58 ML phylogeny but sister to Lineage J in the censored phylogeny (Fig. 3); additionally, the
59 phylogenetic network (Figs. 4a, S3), PCA (Figs. 4C, S7), and Structure results (Figs. 3, S5) all
60 show evidence of admixture between Lineage M and Lineage J in this sample. Another sample
61 of Lineage M from nearby (E026) showed similar patterns, but with less inferred introgression
62 from Lineage J. In contrast to other examples presented here, we hypothesize that this may
63 represent the result of ongoing gene flow among these closely related groups, but further work
64 and better geographic sampling along the French Broad River are necessary to test this idea.

65 Finally, one additional complexity regarding Lineage M and Lineage K+L warrants
66 mention. At one site in the Rich Mountains of northern Georgia, Kozak et al. (2006) found
67 Lineages M and L to be syntopic. We included those same samples in our analysis here (E090
68 and E093) and found discordant results. Sample E093 has an mtDNA genome from Lineage M
69 (Kozak et al. 2006) and indeed belongs to a widespread clade within Lineage M in our analyses

70 (Fig. 3). However, Sample E090—which has an mtDNA from Lineage L (Kozak et al. 2006)—
71 falls out in a very different clade within Lineage M in our analyses (Figs. 3, S4). Furthermore,
72 this clade of Lineage M includes at least two other populations with mtDNA from Lineage L—
73 one from Johns Mountain in the Ridge and Valley of Georgia (E035; Kozak et al. 2006; Timpe et
74 al. 2009) and one from Sosebee Cove further east in the Blue Ridge of Georgia (E043; Camp et
75 al. unpubl. data). At another location, in the Hiwassee River of Tennessee, we found animals
76 from this clade of Lineage M (E038) to be syntopic with Lineage K+L (E037). Thus, there exist
77 several widespread populations of a clade within Lineage M that have mtDNA genomes from
78 Lineage L; this clade is syntopic with another clade of Lineage M in at least one location of the
79 Rich Mountains, and it is syntopic with Lineage L in at least one location along the Hiwassee
80 River. This complex biogeographic pattern warrants much greater attention and suggests an even
81 greater degree of cryptic diversity than what has been previously described.

82

83 *Lineages F, G, and H: monophyly and non-monophyly*

84 In Kozak et al. (2006), an mtDNA clade in the larger southern clade is formed by
85 Lineages F, G, and H. Our new analyses place all three of these groups instead in the northern
86 clade (see main text). Our results support the close relationship between Lineages G and H (i.e.,
87 *Eurycea junaluska* and *E. aquaticus*), and we recovered Lineage F—which is composed of
88 samples from the Emory River drainage, a major tributary of the Tennessee River that drains
89 south and east from the Cumberland Plateau into the Tennessee River valley—as sister to
90 Lineage C, which is found more broadly throughout the Lower Tennessee, Middle Tennessee,
91 and Cumberland River drainages (Figs. 3, S1). Thus, we refer to these collectively as Lineage

92 C+F. In the future, a more careful examination is warranted to examine gene flow where Lineage
93 C+F meets Lineage G+H in the Tennessee River valley.

94 We recovered a clade that corresponds to the traditional geographic distribution of *E.*
95 *junaluska* (i.e., samples E017, E001, E021, E096). However, this made *E. aquatica* (as
96 recognized by Timpe et al. 2009) non-monophyletic, with samples from some populations (E031
97 and E105) more closely related to *E. junaluska* than to populations geographically closer to the
98 type locality of *E. aquatica* in Alabama (i.e., E116 and E117). Furthermore, all of these together
99 were sister to a clade composed of samples from the upper Tennessee River drainage (E044,
100 E022, E020, and E032) and that appear morphologically most similar to *E. aquatica* (Pierson and
101 Miele 2019). Thus, we refer to all of these collectively as Lineage G+H in this manuscript.
102 Species boundaries and gene flow within this group should be reassessed to better inform any
103 recommended taxonomic revisions—especially at the edge of the Blue Ridge escarpment where
104 animals currently classified as *E. aquatica* and *E. junaluska* may come into contact.

105

106 *Lineage E2: evolutionary history of E. wilderae sensu stricto*

107 *E. wilderae sensu stricto* (i.e., Lineage E2) is most closely related *E. arenicola* and
108 Lineage I in the northern clade. The close, but unresolved, relationship among these three groups
109 is epitomized by sample E064. This sample has a mitochondrial genome belonging to Lineage I
110 (Table S1; Kozak et al. 2006), fell out with Lineage E2 in our uncensored ML topology, and was
111 sister to *E. arenicola* in our censored ML topology (Figs. 3, S1). Some of our analyses (e.g.,
112 Figs. 3, S2b) support a close relationship between Lineages E1 and E2, which is consistent with
113 the mtDNA monophyly of these groups. Additionally, our sample from Lineage I (E042) that
114 showed little evidence of introgression from the southern clade comes from very near a site

115 where Kozak et al. (2006) found Lineage E mtDNA. Thus, the future taxonomic assignment of
116 both Lineage E1 and Lineage I remain unclear, but our results confirm their close relationship to
117 *E. wilderae* and *E. arenicola*.

118

119 *Lineages A+B, C, D, and E: post-glacial gene flow*

120 We found distributions of Lineages C and D mostly consistent with those reported in
121 Kozak et al. (2006). One notable exception is our sample E053. This sample from had an
122 mtDNA haplotype within Lineage C in Kozak et al. (2006), but it was sampled from a location
123 with mtDNA haplotypes from both Lineages C and D. In our analyses of 3RAD data, this sample
124 fell out within Lineage D (Fig. 3). In Structure analyses, this sample had a higher (secondary)
125 assignment probability to Lineage C than any other sample within Lineage D (Figs. 3, S6), and
126 in the phylogenetic network, it fell out in a position intermediate between Lineages C and D (Fig.
127 S3). Thus, it may represent either current or historic admixture between these groups in the upper
128 Cumberland River drainage.

129 Our westernmost sample of Lineage E (i.e., E066 in Lineage E1) showed some evidence
130 (i.e., an intermediate position in the phylogenetic network [Figs. 4, S3] and PCA [Fig. S7]) of
131 admixture with Lineage D. Kozak et al. (2006) interpreted the deep divergence between Lineage
132 D and Lineage E—despite both occurring in the modern Ohio River drainage—as evidence of
133 the importance of Miocene and Pliocene paleodrainages, which may have been situated in the
134 Old Ohio and Teays River drainages, respectively. We found evidence mostly consistent with
135 this hypothesis, with Lineage D most closely related to Lineage C+F. However, some
136 phylogenetic (e.g., a subset of bootstrap replicates in the censored phylogeny [Fig. 3]), Structure
137 (Fig. S6), and PCA (Fig. S7) results are consistent with some gene flow between Lineages D and

138 E1, which might have occurred following glacial reorganization of these drainages. We
139 encourage further sampling along contact zones to better describe the distribution of genetic
140 diversity and potential species boundaries among these groups.

141 Finally, we included just a single sample (E100) of the geographically restricted mtDNA
142 Lineage A, and we found it nested within Lineage B (Figs. 3, 4, S3). Thus, we found little
143 evidence for notable biogeographic structure within *E. bislineata* sensu stricto, which may reflect
144 relatively recent range expansions following Pleistocene glaciations (Kozak et al. 2006). We
145 refer to these groups collectively as Lineage A+B. Interactions between Lineage A+B and
146 neighboring groups likewise deserve further attention. Sattler and Brophy (2019) evaluated a
147 contact zone between *E. bislineata* (Lineage A+B) and Lineage E1 in Virginia and argued for a
148 narrow hybrid zone. Guttman and Karlin (1986) examined a contact zone in Ohio—perhaps
149 between Lineage A+B and Lineage D—and likewise found evidence for limited gene flow
150 across a small region. The distributions of Lineages A+B and D, and to some extent, Lineage E,
151 occur largely within regions affected by Pleistocene glaciation, which dramatically reorganized
152 river drainages in the region (Melhorn and Kempton 1991; Andrews 2004) and may have created
153 opportunities for secondary contact and hybridization.

154

155 *A brief clarification regarding previous taxonomic sampling*

156 Although it was not mentioned explicitly in Kozak et al. (2006), the authors of that study
157 believed that samples of what would later be named *Eurycea arenicola* were represented in their
158 dataset as samples from “Population 31”. Subsequent research called that conclusion into
159 question (Stuart et al. 2020). We included one of these samples from Kozak et al. (2006) in our

160 study (E103) and confirmed that it represents Lineage J, not *E. arenicola*. Instead, D. Beamer
161 provided us with fresh material from *E. arenicola*, which is included here as sample E120.

162 As part of the description of *E. arenicola*, Stuart et al. (2020) generated data for 21
163 nuclear loci from a single sample (88) believed to be *E. aquatica*. In their phylogenetic tree and
164 network analyses, they recovered this sample as sister to a sample representing Lineage K.
165 Subsequent mtDNA data and careful examination of this specimen believed to be *E. aquatica*
166 (which was collected from very near the type locality of *E. aquatica*) have revealed that it was
167 instead *E. cirrigera* (i.e., Lineage L; D. Beamer, pers. comm.).

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223 **Table S1. Sampling Localities for Tissue Collection.**

224

Sample	Collection Name	Latitude	Longitude	mtDNA clade	3RAD clade	Species	Left Adapter	Right Adapter	iTru7	iTru5
E001	TWP_224	[withheld]	[withheld]	-	G+H	<i>E. junaluska</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_02	iTru7_006_02	iTru5_002_B
E002	TWP_096	33.8910	-83.3623	-	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_03	iTru7_006_03	iTru5_002_C
E003	TWP_244	35.3575	-83.9178	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_04	iTru7_006_04	iTru5_002_D
E004	TWP_262	37.1857	-80.3766	-	E1	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_06	iTru7_006_06	iTru5_002_F
E005	TWP_264	37.2572	-80.5248	-	E1	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_07	iTru7_006_07	iTru5_002_G
E006	TWP_265	39.4288	-76.9232	-	A+B	<i>E. bislineata</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_08	iTru7_006_08	iTru5_002_H
E007	TWP_266	37.3566	-80.461	-	E1	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_09	iTru7_006_09	iTru5_001_A
E008	TWP_272	34.4027	-83.5921	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_10	iTru7_006_10	iTru5_001_B
E009	KHK_336	35.3872	-79.9622	J	J	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_11	iTru7_006_11	iTru5_001_C
E010	KHK_06	35.61	-83.45	M	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_12	iTru7_006_12	iTru5_001_D
E011	KHK_7.1411	32.50	-83.50	L	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_01	iTru7_007_01	iTru5_001_E
E012	KHK_7.109	34.9314	-82.3832	M	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_02	iTru7_007_02	iTru5_001_F
E013	KHK_8.172	35.39	-82.75	M	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_03	iTru7_007_03	iTru5_001_G
E014	KHK_8.288	35.50	-84.02	M	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_04	iTru7_007_04	iTru5_001_H
E015	KW_0963	[withheld]	[withheld]	-	-	<i>E. wallacei</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_02	iTru7_007_06	iTru5_007_B
E016	KW_0960	[withheld]	[withheld]	-	-	<i>E. wallacei</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_03	iTru7_007_07	iTru5_007_C
E017	TWP_103	[withheld]	[withheld]	-	G+H	<i>E. junaluska</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_05	iTru7_007_09	iTru5_007_E
E018	TWP_118	35.7972	-84.8117	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_06	iTru7_007_10	iTru5_007_F
E019	TWP_121	35.3977	-84.0736	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_07	iTru7_007_11	iTru5_007_G
E020	TWP_226	36.2060	-82.6508	-	G+H	<i>E. aquatica</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_08	iTru7_007_12	iTru5_007_H
E021	TWP_153	[withheld]	[withheld]	-	G+H	<i>E. junaluska</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_09	iTru7_008_01	iTru5_006_A
E022	TWP_155	35.9564	-83.9224	-	G+H	<i>E. aquatica</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_10	iTru7_008_02	iTru5_006_B
E023	TWP_156	36.1249	-84.423	-	C+F	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_11	iTru7_008_03	iTru5_006_C
E024	TWP_159	36.1260	-84.5045	-	C+F	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_12	iTru7_008_04	iTru5_006_D

E025	TWP_167	35.8410	-82.9689	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_01	iTru7_008_05	iTru5_006_E
E026	TWP_170	35.8253	-82.9375	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_02	iTru7_008_06	iTru5_006_F
E027	TWP_175	35.9613	-82.8752	-	J	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_03	iTru7_008_07	iTru5_006_G
E028	TWP_179	35.6728	-85.3851	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_04	iTru7_008_08	iTru5_006_H
E029	TWP_190	35.2516	-85.7464	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_05	iTru7_008_09	iTru5_005_A
E030	TWP_191	35.2516	-85.7464	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_06	iTru7_008_10	iTru5_005_B
E031	TWP_193	34.9759	-85.2406	-	G+H	<i>E. aquatica</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_07	iTru7_008_11	iTru5_005_C
E032	TWP_194	35.9507	-83.8768	-	G+H	<i>E. aquatica</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_08	iTru7_008_12	iTru5_005_D
E033	TWP_203	35.1873	-84.4879	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_09	iTru7_009_01	iTru5_005_E
E034	TWP_233	35.7445	-82.214	-	J	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_10	iTru7_009_02	iTru5_005_F
E035	TWP_238	34.6705	-85.0618	-	M	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_11	iTru7_009_03	iTru5_005_G
E036	TWP_242	34.2161	-84.6834	-	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_12	iTru7_009_04	iTru5_005_H
E037	TWP_247	35.1982	-84.3708	-	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_01	iTru7_009_05	iTru5_004_A
E038	TWP_248	35.1936	-84.3822	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_02	iTru7_009_06	iTru5_004_B
E039	TWP_255	31.1865	-89.1375	-	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_03	iTru7_009_07	iTru5_004_C
E040	TWP_254	33.2511	-88.9817	-	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_04	iTru7_009_08	iTru5_004_D
E041	TWP_259	33.4283	-84.9467	-	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_05	iTru7_009_09	iTru5_004_E
E042	TWP_260	36.7812	-80.3795	-	I	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_06	iTru7_009_10	iTru5_004_F
E043	TWP_271	34.7851	-83.9336	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_10	iTru7_010_02	iTru5_003_B
E044	TWP_273	36.2502	-83.9290	-	G+H	<i>E. aquatica</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_11	iTru7_010_03	iTru5_003_C
E045	KHK_615	36.2880	-81.6492	E	E2	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_12	iTru7_010_04	iTru5_003_D
E046	KHK_595	35.8503	-81.9855	J	J	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_01	iTru7_010_05	iTru5_003_E
E047	KHK_596	35.8503	-81.9855	J	J	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_02	iTru7_010_06	iTru5_003_F
E048	KHK_448	35.1408	-81.3458	J	J	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_03	iTru7_010_07	iTru5_003_G
E049	KHK_727	35.7813	-85.0198	M	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_04	iTru7_010_08	iTru5_003_H
E050	KHK_199	31.0422	-89.0717	L	L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_01	iTru7_010_09	iTru5_010_D
E051	KHK_373	36.2737	-86.9028	C	C	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_02	iTru7_010_10	iTru5_010_E
E052	KHK_688	35.6253	-86.3165	C	C	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_03	iTru7_010_11	iTru5_010_F
E053	KHK_402	36.8468	-85.2118	C	D	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_04	iTru7_010_12	iTru5_010_G

E054	KHK_8.331	34.08	-82.34	L	L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_05	iTru7_011_01	iTru5_010_H
E055	KHK_469	35.8217	-78.7883	J	J	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_06	iTru7_011_02	iTru5_009_A
E056	KHK_378	37.0838	-87.0312	D	D	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_07	iTru7_011_03	iTru5_009_B
E057	KHK_416	37.7825	-83.6732	D	D	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_08	iTru7_011_04	iTru5_009_C
E058	KHK_426	36.0703	-84.5447	F	F	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_09	iTru7_011_05	iTru5_009_D
E059	KHK_8.17	30.33	-84.50	L	L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_10	iTru7_011_06	iTru5_009_E
E060	KHK_186	31.0957	-89.2138	L	L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_11	iTru7_011_07	iTru5_009_F
E061	KHK_8.98	35.10	-83.68	M	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_12	iTru7_011_08	iTru5_009_G
E062	KHK_735	36.2737	-86.9028	C	C	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_01	iTru7_011_09	iTru5_009_H
E063	KHK_374	37.0558	-87.6442	D	D	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_02	iTru7_011_10	iTru5_008_A
E064	KHK_506	35.9647	-81.3145	I	E2	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_03	iTru7_011_11	iTru5_008_B
E065	KHK_159	39.00	-84.72	D	D	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_04	iTru7_011_12	iTru5_008_C
E066	KHK_71203	37.9905	-82.3502	E	E1	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_05	iTru7_012_01	iTru5_008_D
E067	KHK_562	38.9242	-78.3313	B	B	<i>E. bislineata</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_06	iTru7_012_02	iTru5_008_E
E068	KHK_730	36.0013	-84.5086	F	F	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_07	iTru7_012_03	iTru5_008_F
E069	KHK_H-1915	34.5875	-88.1917	L	L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_08	iTru7_012_04	iTru5_008_G
E070	KHK_391	37.2121	-86.1379	D	D	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_09	iTru7_012_05	iTru5_008_H
E071	TWP_106	35.6838	-83.5380	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_01	iTru7_012_06	iTru5_012_D
E072	TWP_325	36.2376	-84.1198	-	C+F	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_02	iTru7_012_07	iTru5_012_E
E073	TWP_319	35.1847	-85.8683	-	C+F	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_03	iTru7_012_08	iTru5_012_F
E074	TWP_051	34.9541	-83.5527	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_04	iTru7_012_09	iTru5_012_G
E075	TWP_084	33.8910	-83.3623	-	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_05	iTru7_012_10	iTru5_012_H
E076	TWP_295	35.7744	-83.1122	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_06	iTru7_012_11	iTru5_011_A
E077	TWP_299	35.9634	-82.8667	-	J	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_07	iTru7_012_12	iTru5_011_B
E078	TWP_300	35.9634	-82.8667	-	J	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_08	iTru7_013_01	iTru5_011_C
E079	TWP_196	36.0371	-81.9083	-	E2	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_09	iTru7_013_02	iTru5_011_D
E080	TWP_304	35.3575	-83.9178	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_10	iTru7_013_03	iTru5_011_E
E081	TWP_219	35.9955	-84.4767	-	C+F	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_11	iTru7_013_04	iTru5_011_F

E082	TWP_195	36.0371	-81.9083	-	E2	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_12	iTru7_013_05	iTru5_011_G
E083	TWP_309	35.7410	-83.0743	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_01	iTru7_013_06	iTru5_011_H
E084	TWP_311	35.7832	-83.1162	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_02	iTru7_013_07	iTru5_010_A
E085	TWP_306	35.7445	-83.0086	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_03	iTru7_013_08	iTru5_010_B
E086	TWP_307	35.7832	-83.1162	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_04	iTru7_013_09	iTru5_010_C
E087	KHK_492	36.3932	-80.2693	I	I	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_01	iTru7_013_10	iTru5_001_A
E088	KHK_525	37.8777	-79.8097	E	E1	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_02	iTru7_013_11	iTru5_001_B
E089	KHK_485	36.4825	-77.9677	I	I	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_03	iTru7_013_12	iTru5_001_C
E090	KHK_49	34.7280	-84.378	L	M	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_05	iTru7_006_02	iTru5_001_E
E091	KHK_397	37.0838	-87.0312	D	D	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_06	iTru7_006_03	iTru5_001_F
E092	KHK_536	40.68	-74.38	B	B	<i>E. bislineata</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_07	iTru7_006_04	iTru5_001_G
E093	KHK_50	34.7280	-84.378	M	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_08	iTru7_006_05	iTru5_001_H
E094	KHK_7.104	35.05	-83.19	M	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_09	iTru7_006_06	iTru5_002_A
E095	KHK_199	31.0422	-89.0717	L	L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_10	iTru7_006_07	iTru5_002_B
E096	KHK_8.28	[withheld]	[withheld]	G	G	<i>E. junaluska</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_11	iTru7_006_08	iTru5_002_C
E097	KHK_607	36.038	-81.910	E	E2	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_12	iTru7_006_09	iTru5_002_D
E098	KHK_602	36.038	-81.910	E	E2	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_01	iTru7_006_10	iTru5_002_E
E099	KHK_420	37.801	-83.767	D	D	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_02	iTru7_006_11	iTru5_002_F
E100	KHK_574	38.4662	-78.5017	A	A	<i>E. bislineata</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_03	iTru7_006_12	iTru5_002_G
E101	KHK_261	35.3775	-87.5117	C	C	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_04	iTru7_007_01	iTru5_002_H
E102	KHK_605	36.038	-81.910	M	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_05	iTru7_007_02	iTru5_003_A
E103	KHK_466	35.310	-79.250	J	J	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_06	iTru7_007_03	iTru5_003_B
E104	KHK_246	35.5998	-87.7727	C	C	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_07	iTru7_007_04	iTru5_003_C
E105	TWP_077	34.900	-84.9767	-	G+H	<i>E. aquatica</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_09	iTru7_007_06	iTru5_003_E
E106	TWP_109	36.7188	-81.5204	-	E2	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_03	iTru7_007_08	iTru5_003_G
E107	TWP_111	36.6400	-81.5884	-	E2	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_04	iTru7_007_09	iTru5_003_H
E108	TWP_112	35.7864	-85.0146	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_05	iTru7_007_10	iTru5_004_A
E109	TWP_114	35.7972	-84.8117	-	-	<i>E. longicauda</i>	NheI_F	EcoRI_06	iTru7_007_11	iTru5_004_B
E110	TWP_129	36.0748	-84.5421	-	C+F	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_G	EcoRI_07	iTru7_007_12	iTru5_004_C

E111	TWP_124	30.5022	-84.2156	-	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_H	EcoRI_08	iTru7_008_01	iTru5_004_D
E112	TWP_031	34.9479	-83.5523	-	M	<i>E. wilderae</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_09	iTru7_008_02	iTru5_004_E
E113	TWP_046	34.9915	-83.5566	-	-	<i>E. guttolineata</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_10	iTru7_008_03	iTru5_004_F
E114	TWP_061	30.8512	-84.8097	-	-	<i>E. quadridigitata</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_11	iTru7_008_04	iTru5_004_G
E115	TWP_263	37.3781	-80.2442	-	E1	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_01	iTru7_013_09	iTru5_010_E
E116	TWP_269	34.0138	-87.3583	-	G+H	<i>E. aquatica</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_02	iTru7_013_10	iTru5_010_F
E117	TWP_270	33.8831	-86.581	-	G+H	<i>E. aquatica</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_03	iTru7_006_03	iTru5_001_C
E118	KHK_53644	35.3130	-79.2616	-	J	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_E	EcoRI_05	iTru7_008_09	iTru5_002_D
E119	KHK_53647	35.3130	-79.2616	J	J	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_06	iTru7_008_10	iTru5_002_E
E120	DB_9660	35.0280	-79.6377	-	<i>E. arenicola</i>	<i>E. arenicola</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_07	iTru7_008_11	iTru5_002_F
E121	DB_2171	30.9420	-89.9783	-	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_A	EcoRI_01	iTru7_010_01	iTru5_011_A
E122	KHK_H1873	30.83	-90.20	K	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_B	EcoRI_02	iTru7_010_02	iTru5_011_B
E123	KHK_H1874	30.83	-90.20	K	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_C	EcoRI_03	iTru7_010_03	iTru5_011_C
E124	KHK_H532	30.83	-90.20	K	K+L	<i>E. cirrigera</i>	NheI_D	EcoRI_04	iTru7_010_04	iTru5_011_D

225

226 Adapter and primer (iTru7 and iTru5) names correspond to unique indexes as detailed Bayona-Vásquez et al. (2019). Out of an
227 abundance of caution (and due to a request by the National Park Service), we have withheld the locality information for samples of *E.*
228 *junaluska*; we have done the same for *E. wallacei*. Mitochondrial (mtDNA) clade is provided only for samples from Kozak et al.
229 (2006); 3RAD clade reflects results from the uncensored maximum-likelihood phylogeny shown in Fig. 3; species names reflect the
230 most widely adopted taxonomy, which is described by Sever (1972), Sever (1999), and Stuart et al. (2020) and is largely reflective of
231 relationships described in Jacobs (1987).

232

Figure S1.

Figure S2.

Figure S3.

Figure S4.

Figure S5.

Figure S6.

Figure S7.

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure S1: Map of samples from the northern clade. Shading shows elevation, and blue lines represent major modern rivers.

Figure S2: Map of samples from the southern clade. Shading shows elevation, and blue lines represent major modern rivers.

Figure S3: Labeled Neighbor-Net phylogenetic network inferred from the: a) *full_min30* assembly; b) *north* assembly; and c) *south* assembly.

Figure S4: Delta K plots for Structure analyses using a) all samples; b) only samples from the northern clade; and c) only samples from the southern clade.

Figure S5: Assignments from Structure analyses of all samples for $K = 2-10$.

Figure S6: Assignments from Structure analyses of samples from the northern clade for $K = 2-7$.

Figure S7: The first two axes of a principal components analysis from the a) *north* assembly; and b) *south* assembly.